

COVID-19 pandemic-associated medical waste emerging ecological catastrophe and the need for more rational approach to medical masks usage

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ABSTRACT

The amount of medical waste generated from COVID-19 since the outbreak is estimated to be 2.6 million tons/day worldwide and is still growing. Such an amount of medical waste can be also attributable to global mask mandates which are still in force despite the global vaccine rollout. As the Wuhan spike protein-based vaccines have waning efficacy against transmission of new variants, medical mask mandates are still applicable, but there is a need to discuss more focused approach when it comes to medical masks recommendations/mandates in a incidence-dependent manner, meaning that higher the new COVID-19 cases stronger should be the recommendations/mandates, and *vice versa*, in case of significantly lower incidence of new COVID-19 cases, recommendations/mandates should be relieved. There is also a need for the development of new technologies in medical masks manufacturing towards easily recyclable and biodegradable protective medical equipment, if possible, as well as the need for the improvement of existing technologies for medical waste sanitation. Open scientific debate on the ecological sustainability in the context of COVID-19 pandemic is mandatory.

Keywords: COVID-19; medical waste; ecological catastrophe; medical masks

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 pandemic is caused by respiratory virus SARS-CoV-2, for the prevention of which are used various types of medical and non-medical masks, that are being mandated globally from the very beginning of the pandemic not only for

healthcare workers, but for the general population as well. Mask mandates vary from universal use of masks to more rationale, and focused approach of medical masks use, such as for health care workers, for vulnerable population, only during the pandemic peaks.

Feng and coworkers recommended that it would be rational that people in quarantine wear face masks if they need to leave home for any reason, to prevent potential asymptomatic or pre-symptomatic transmission. Vulnerable populations, such as older adults and those with underlying medical conditions, should wear face masks if available. Important reason to discourage widespread use of face masks is to preserve limited supplies for professional use in health-care settings. Universal face mask use in the community has also been discouraged with the argument that face masks provide no effective protection against coronavirus infection¹.

Masks used in general population vary from non-medical masks, such as cloth masks; surgical masks, which must be changed at least every 4-6 hours; and respirator masks, which provide the best, although not absolute, protection against COVID-19 (FFP2, FFP3, N95). There is a dilemma how to strike a fair balance between protection of population against transmission of SARS-CoV-2 on the one hand and prevention of ecological catastrophe on the other hand. Reusable non-medical masks offer poor or no protection against COVID-19, but are more environmentally friendly. Non-reusable medical masks, especially

respirator masks offer better protection, but unfortunately generate more medical waste. Despite the global Wuhan spike-protein based vaccines rollout, and because of the waning efficacy of the vaccines against transmission of new variants, especially omicron and IHU, which are heavily mutated in the spike protein, masks mandates remained in force up today, generating more and more medical waste and increasing the ecological burden on the planet.

COVID-19 pandemic-related medical waste emerging ecological catastrophe

The amount of medical waste generated from COVID-19 since the outbreak is estimated to be 2.6 million tons/day worldwide². The majority of the world's discarded waste from COVID-19, particularly personal protective equipment, ends up in landfills, rivers, and oceans, compounding the existing plastics threat to the planet's ecosystems. If 1% of face masks generated during the pandemic are inappropriately disposed of, about 10 million face masks will end up polluting the environment each month³. Actions to ensure the safe and environmentally sound management of COVID-19 waste can prevent undesirable health and environmental impacts arising from the release of chemical

or biological threats and drug-resistant pathogens into the environment, helping to protect the health of patients, medical workers, and the general public².

One of the major negative aspects of COVID-19 pandemic is the overlooking of the environmental aspects and the evoking catastrophes of increased plastic pollution all over the world⁴. The results of systematic literature review from prominent databases to portray the environmental issues that emerged during the COVID-19 pandemic from a policy perspective indicates very limited policy issued by the governments to protect the environment for the post-covid era⁵. The global warming potential of municipal solid waste (MSW) and solid medical waste (SMW) vary from -0.64 to 520 kg CO₂ equiv/tonne and -52.1 to 3730 kg CO₂ equiv/tonne. MSW and SMW disposal costs vary from 90 to \$242/tonne and 12 to \$1430.0/tonne. COVID-19 pandemic affected waste segregation and recycling, and is associated with an increase use of single-use plastics to prevent transmission of COVID-19⁶. Growing amount of medical waste as well as single-use plastics generated during this pandemic is an emerging ecological catastrophe that should be openly discussed and mitigated urgently.

CONCLUSION

Global mask mandates during COVID-19 pandemic have contributed to the growing medical waste burden on our planet. As SARS-CoV-2 is a respiratory virus, high quality medical masks, primarily respirator masks (FFP2, FFP3, N95), can help in the mitigation of COVID-19 pandemic and can slow down the spread of the virus, but do not represent an absolute protection. There is a need to strike a fair balance between public health demands on the one hand and ecological sustainability of our planet on the other hand, which is as important as epidemiological measures, because severe pollution caused by excessive medical waste accumulation will severely harm the public health. More focused approach to mask mandates is necessary, because universal face masks mandates are not sustainable. High quality respirator masks should be recommended for health care workers; vulnerable individuals and all professional and family care givers that interact with vulnerable individuals, but only during that interaction; for individuals infected with COVID-19 to allow them to leave the quarantine with a respirator mask if absolutely necessary.

These recommendations/mandates should be also modeled in an incidence-dependent manner, meaning that higher level of recommendation for medical masks use should be established during the pandemic peaks, in order to flatten the curve and relieve the burden on health care systems, and on the other hand, these recommendations/mandates should be relieved when the numbers of new COVID-19 cases are significantly lower. Also, taking into account that non-medical reusable masks offer poor or no protection against COVID-19, but are more environmentally friendly, and that respirator non-reusable medical masks offer better protection against the transmission of the virus, but also generate more medical waste, there is a need to explore new technologies in medical masks manufacturing, such as biodegradable and easily recyclable medical protective equipment, if possible, and improve existing technologies of medical waste sanitation. As Wuhan spike protein-based vaccines have waning efficacy against the transmission of new strains, especially omicron and IHU, which are heavily mutated in the spike protein, there is a need for the second generation of COVID-19 vaccines, possibly based on the non-spike epitopes in

order to ensure longer-lasting and cross-reactive immunity against new strains, which would consequently reduce the need for medical masks mandates. Research on effective prophylactic agents could also reduce the need for medical masks usage. And finally, there is a strong need for raising awareness of ecological consequences related to generation of medical waste associated with COVID-19 pandemic and the need for open scientific debate on this issue.

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